

A Study on Job Satisfaction of Women Employees of Private Sector Banks in Ramanathapuram Town

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Abstract

In the present study, based on survey of perception of women employees in private banking sector in Ramanathapuram town. On the basis of the response of 100 respondents. The study aims to measure the level of study Job satisfaction, Job involvement and organizational climate of women employees in private banking sector in Ramanathapuram town.

Introduction

Job satisfaction is the state of mind. It refers to the level of satisfaction of an employee derives in discharging his duties. Job satisfaction is the amount of pleasure or contentment associated with the job. It is an individual's emotional reaction to the job itself. Keith Dave's said that "Job satisfaction is the favorableness or unfavorableness with which employees view their work". A staff may be satisfied when his expectations are fulfilled. Job satisfaction describes how content an individual is with his or her job. It is feelings which individual may have that their important needs are satisfied by the work they are doing. As a result, they will express a favorable attitude to their job.

Statement of the problem

The study is also focused on the specific factors which influence the job satisfaction of the private bank employees. The private banks are managed by the employees (i.e.) from the managers to the lowest level employees. All of them are employees except the Board of Directors in the private sector banks. The level of satisfaction may differ from one level to another level depending on the policies, rules, salary conditions, environment motivation and like. So, the researcher has undertaken the research on the topic "A Study on Job Satisfaction of Women employees in Private Banks in Ramanathapuram town".

Scope of the Study

This study is emphasized on the job satisfaction of the women employees of Private sector banks in Ramanathapuram town.

Methodology and Research Design

The Present study is empirical. The questionnaire method is adopted as the instrument of collecting data directly from 100 employees in Ramanathapuram town, through convenience sampling. The Primary data collected directly by the researcher and Secondary data were collected from various books, journals, magazines, etc.

The Period of Study

The period of study is confined to about four years i.e. From June 2018 to December 2018. The statistical tools such as percentage analysis, Chi -square test, are used for data analysis and interpreted.

Objectives of the Study

1. To measure the Job satisfaction level of the women employees of private sector banks in Ramanathapuram town.
2. To study the job involvement of the women employees of private sector banks in Ramanathapuram town.
3. To examine the impact of the organizational climate on women employees of private sector banks in Ramanathapuram town.

Result and Discussion

Age Wise of Classification

Age is an important factor which influencing the job satisfaction of women employees in Private Sector Banks. The researcher has interviewed the various age groups of the respondents and the details are presented in the following table.

Table 1 Age wise of classification

S.No	Age	No.of.Respondents	Percentage
1	Below 25 Years	34	34
2	25 – 35 Years	25	25
3	35 – 45 Years	24	24
4	Above 45 Years	17	17
	Total	100	100

Source : Primary Data

From the above table 1 it is clear that out of 100 respondents 34 percent of the respondents are in the age group of below 25 years, 25 percent of the respondent are between 25 and 35 years, 24 Percent of the respondents are between 35 and 45 years and remaining 17 percent of the respondents are above 45 years of age.

It is found that majority of 34 respondents were in the age group of below 25 years. It is understood that Private Sector Banks in the study area giving opportunity to young women employees to enter into Banking jobs.

Educational Qualification

The Educational level is one of the important factors which affects the job satisfaction level of the Bank employees. The researcher has made an attempt to analyze the educational level of the respondents and the details are resented in the following table.

Table 2 Educational qualification

S.No	Educational level	No.of.Respondents	Percentage
1	Under Graduate	29	29
2	Post Graduate	23	23
3	Professional	24	24
4	Diploma	24	24
	Total	100	100

Source : Primary Data

It is clear from the above Table 2 that out 100 respondents. 29 percent of the respondents are studied up to Degree level, 24 percent of the respondent are professional level, 24 percent of the respondent are Diploma level and the remaining 23 percent of the them are having post graduate level education.

It is interesting to note that most of the respondents are degree holders. It is understood that Private Sector Banks expect minimum of degree level knowledge for appointing as an employees in their branches.

Number of income earners

An attempt has been made by the researcher to know the income earners of the respondents and the details are presented in the table 3.

Table 3 Income Earners of the Respondents

S.No	Number of Income Earners	No.of.Respondents	Percentage
1	One	52	52
2	Two	36	36
3	More than Two	12	12
	Total	100	100

Source : Primary Data

From the above table 3 it is clear that 52 percent of the respondents are having only one member under income earning capacity, 36 percent of the respondents are having Tow members and the remaining 12 percent of the respondents are having more than two members in their family under income earning category. It is found that most of the respondents family is having only one members under Income earning capacity.

Nature of Post of the Respondents

An attempt has been made by the researcher to know the nature of post held by the respondents in the banks and the details are presented in the Table 4.

Table 4 Nature of Post of the Respondents

S.No	Nature of post	No.of.Respondents	Percentage
1	Clerk	62	62
2	Assistant manager	17	17
3	Chief manager	11	11
4	Deputy Manager	10	10
	Total	100	100

Source : Primary Data

The above table 4 highlights the fact that, out of 100 respondents ,62 percent of the respondents are working as clerk,17 percent of the respondents are assistant manager and another 11 percent Chief manager, remaining 10 percent of the respondents are working as Deputy manager. it is found that most of the respondents are working as clerk in the private sector banks.

Reception towards job satisfaction of women employees

The researcher has gathered the details from the women employees of Private Sector to measure the level of job satisfaction. For this purpose over all opinion of the respondents are gathered by using. The statements and the score is obtained through relative scale values. Then on the basis of the score the job satisfaction level is measured and the same is presented in the following table.

Table 5 Perception towards Job Satisfaction among Women Employees

S.No	Job Satisfaction	No.of.Respondents	Percentage
1	Highly Satisfied	32	32
2	Moderately Satisfied	42	42
3	Dissatisfied	26	26
	Total	100	100

Source : Primary Data

It is clear from the above table 5 that out of 100 respondents interviewed 32 respondents have expressed that they are highly satisfied towards their job, 42 respondents are moderately satisfied towards their job and the remaining 26 respondents are dissatisfaction with their job. It is found that, majority of the Private Sector Banks they are satisfied with their job is a welcoming feature.

Job Involvement of the Respondents

The statement and the score is obtained through relative scale value. Then on the basis of the score the job involvement level is measured and the same presented in the following table.

Table 6 Level of Job Involvement of Women Employees

S.No	Job Involvement	No.of.Respondents	Percentage
1	High Level	31	31
2	Moderate Level	37	37
3	Low Level	32	32
	Total	100	100

Source : Primary Data

The above table 6 clearly shows that, 37 respondents are having Moderate involvement 31 respondents are having a high involvement and the remaining 32 respondents are having Low level of involvement in their job. It is found that most of the women employees are having involvement in their jobs in Private Sector Banks in the Study area.

Perception towards Organisation Climate

The researcher has gathered the details from the respondents about their organizational climate under different dimensions like professional help, Formalization, Professional Management, Organisation Risk Taking, Standardization, People organization, Centralization, Formulization communication, Welfare concern. Therefore Nine aspects are analysed with statement and the score is obtained. The results are presented in the following table.

Table 7 Perception towards Organisation Climate

S.No	Job Satisfaction	No.of.Respondents	Percentage
1	Good	33	33
2	Moderate	44	44
3	Poor	23	23
	Total	100	100

Source : Primary Data

The above table 7 shows that, 44 percent women employees are having moderate perception with their organizational climate, 33 percent of the respondents having good perception towards their organizational climate and the remaining 23 percent of the respondents are having poor perception towards organizational climate. It is found that most of the respondents are having moderate perception towards their organizational climate of the Private Sector Banks in the Study are is motivating the women employees to do the Better performance in their concerned job.

Testing of Hypothesis

H1 :There is no significant association between the age and Job satisfaction level of the respondents.

An attempt has been made by the researcher to know the relationship between age of the respondents and their job satisfaction level. For this purpose the following table is constructed by using age and job satisfaction level of the respondents.

Table 8 Age and Job Satisfaction Level of the Respondents

S.No	Age	Highly Satisfied	Moderate satisfied	Dissatisfied	Total
1	Below 25 Years	16	16	2	34
2	25 to 35 Years	4	16	5	25
3	35 to 45 Years	8	8	8	24
4	Above 45 Years	4	2	11	17
	Total	32	42	26	100

Source : Primary Data

For 6 Degrees of freedom at 5% level of significations is 27, 91. The calculate value is greater than the table value. Therefore the null hypothesis rejected. Hence there is significant difference between age and job satisfaction of the respondents.

Testing Hypothesis

H2: There is no significant association between the age and Job Involvement level of the respondents.

An attempt has been made by the researcher to known the relationship between age of the respondents and their job involvement level. For this purpose the following table is constructed by using age level and opinion level of job involvement of the respondents.

Table 9 Age and job involvement level of the respondents

S.No	Age	Low Involvement	Moderate Involvement	High Involvement	Total
1	Below 25 Years	20	8	6	34
2	25 to 35 Years	5	12	8	25
3	35 to 45 Years	6	13	5	24
4	Above 45 Years	11	4	12	17
	Total	32	37	39	100

Source : Primary Data

For 6 Degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance is 30, 31. The calculate is greater than the table value. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is significant difference between the age and job involvement level of the respondents.

Suggestions

A detailed analysis of job satisfaction of women employees of the banking industry has been made and researcher has offered the following suggestions for the better improvement of the women employees of private sector banks in Ramanathapuram town.

- The women employees in private sector banks are more concerned with relationships of other employees. The friendly and supportive colleagues lead to increased job satisfaction and higher productivity in banks.
- The banks may boost women employee's morale by providing different types of job performing opportunities, extension works and challenging job assignments instead of giving monotonous work in banks.
- Appointment of additional staff is necessary in banks to reduce the work load of the women bank employees in Private Sector Banks.
- The bank management must take necessary step to provide promotion to women employees at the right time and to the right person.
- Good amount of concessions, incentives and encouragement may also provide to the women employees. This will go a long way to improve the morale of the women employees.

Conclusion

The value of women employees can be enhanced by given that inspiration and job satisfaction. The job satisfaction is related to the inherent way of thinking of the women employees. The inherent feelings may become optimistic only when women employees are satisfied with the job, the management can attain the desired goals.

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